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DEONTOLOGICAL STANDARDS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF LEGAL SERVICES IN THE SPHERE OF AGRIBUSINESS

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the deontological aspects of legal services in the field of agribusiness. Land is the basis of the functioning of the agro-industrial complex, a factor in the economic well-being of national states, and in modern conditions, land is also a subject of conflict due to the growing demand for food, fuel, housing and natural resources. Management plays an important role in making decisions about land use and access to it, developing the potential of land, and its rational use is crucial. In modern society, the influence of land use, land use and distribution of land rights is changing. The modern dimension of the functioning of agribusiness does not allow obtaining the maximum profit and social result without using the latest forms of business organization. The legal service at agribusiness enterprises is designed not only to provide legal support for the operation of the enterprise, but also to outline the legitimate boundaries of the agribusiness, to represent a fundamental understanding of the key concepts necessary for the successful management of agribusiness in a rapidly changing, high-tech, consumer-oriented and uncertain world.

According to deontological standards, a legal adviser is obliged to strive for development, improvement and to promote creative solutions.

Keywords: deontological directions, legal service, agribusiness sphere.

Анотація. Агробізнес – це особлива підсистема економічних відносин, що складається в аграрному секторі розвинутих країн у результаті об'єднання аграрного, промислового і торговельного капіталу в процесі посилення інтеграційних зв'язків між сільським господарством і промисловістю. Це один із видів соціально-економічного розвитку, запорука збереження продовольчої безпеки країни. Результативність та ефективність аграрного сектору залежить від багатьох факторів, а особливо від впровадження новітніх наукових розробок у сфері господарювання. Ціннісні атрактори ролі адвокатури полягають у тому, що захист інтересів особи є пріоритетною роллю фахівця в галузі права. Пошук партнерства передбачає значну роль юридичних консультантів у налагодженні зв'язків між агробізнесом та місцевими територіальними громадами. Обов'язком юрисконсульта також має бути забезпечення інтересів громадянського суспільства.

Стаття присвячена деонтологічним аспектам надання юридичних послуг у сфері агробізнесу. Земля є основою функціонування агропромислового комплексу, фактором економічного добробуту національних держав, а в сучасних умовах земля є ще й предметом конкуренції через зростання попиту на продукти харчування, паливо, житло та природні ресурси. Управління відіграє важливу роль у прийнятті рішень щодо землекористування та доступу до нього, розвитку потенціалу землі, а її раціональне використання має вирішальне значення. У сучасному суспільстві змінюється роль

землекористування, а також землекористування і розподілу прав на землю. Сучасний вимір функціонування агробізнесу не дозволяє отримати максимальний прибуток і соціальний результат без використання новітніх форм організації бізнесу. Юридична служба на підприємствах АПК покликана не тільки забезпечити юридичний супровід діяльності підприємства, а й окреслити законні підстави агробізнесу, представити фундаментальне розуміння ключових понять, необхідних для успішного ведення агробізнесу в умовах мінливого, високотехнологічного, орієнтованого на споживача світ.

Згідно з деонтологічними стандартами, юрисконсульт зобов'язаний прагнути до розвитку, вдосконалення та просувати творчі рішення.

Ключові слова: деонтологічні напрями, юридична служба, сфера агробізнесу.

Introduction

Agribusiness is a special subsystem of economic relations created in the agrarian sector of developed countries as a result of the unification of agrarian, industrial and trade capital in the process of strengthening the integration ties between agriculture and industry [1]. It is one of the types of social and economic development, a guarantee of preserving the country's food security. The effectiveness and efficiency of the agricultural sector depends on many factors, especially on the implementation of the latest scientific developments - innovations - in the field of management.

The value attractors of the role of the legal profession are that protecting the interests of a person is the priority role of a specialist in the field of law. The search for partnership involves a significant role of legal counsel in establishing ties between agribusiness and local territorial communities. The legal adviser's responsibility should also be to ensure the interests of civil society.

Analysis of recent researches and publications. An important task of deontology consists not only in the education of moral legal standards, but also in the developed needs of their application in practice. Scientists such as Dentoni D., Bijman J., Bossle M.B., Gondwe S., Isubikalu P., Ji C., Kella C., Pascucci S., Royer A., Vieira, L., Chamberlain W., Anseeuw W., Rosete R., Wu R., Lo C., Liu N. believe that "dry" legal knowledge cannot fully meet the modern requirements of the time, guaranteeing the proper functioning of an enterprise or organization in any field legal service, and here the task of its employees is to provide legal support and create an appropriate legal, including moral and ethical field of functioning of a legal entity based on the principles of equality, non-discrimination, legality and the rule of law.

Formulation of the goals of the article (statement of the task). Within the scope of this topic, it is important to study the peculiarities of deontological axiological principles in the functioning of the legal service in agribusiness.

Results

Updating the legal field, reforming legal norms, changing the social and legal reality necessitates the formation of an effective class of human rights defenders. In the context of the development of an independent Ukrainian state, there is an urgent need for highly qualified specialists in the field of agribusiness. The legal profession, from a regulatory point of view, should consist in mastering regulatory and legal information and provide for the possibility of applying knowledge in practice. However, modern society cannot exist within such narrow frameworks. Law is only one of the possible regulators of social relations. Additional norms, principles, rules of behavior that exist in society, including morality, religion, corporate norms, cultural paradigms, etc., cannot be rejected. So, now we should talk about moving away from the "dry" normative legalistic approach in the legal profession and expanding it by implementing the moral and value achievements of humanity. Such a process can provide deontological direction of legal awareness. S.S. Slyvka noted that "the deontological legal awareness of a lawyer is the result of his legal awareness, formed under the influence of legal information culture, while performing official duty" [2, p.107].

Deontological legal awareness is formed through the accumulation and functional interaction of many elements. Most scientists agree that its mandatory components should be: legal knowledge, a high level of respect for the law, political-legal and social activity of a person.

The legal service in the ministries, other central bodies of the state executive power, at the state enterprise, in the institution, organization is represented by the work of legal advisers, as the main specialists in the legal field

The work of a legal adviser consists in advising state or non-state institutions on legal issues. However, the modern approach to the functioning of a specialist in the field of law cannot be limited exclusively to a normative approach. Technological convergence has consequences not only for human rights and the ways of their realization, but also for the fundamental concept of what characterizes a person. Social perceptions of risk and the geopolitical context profoundly influence the legal approach to uncertainty. Thus, convergent technologies cause us to take a new, broader view of the concept of legal specialty and legal education.

Knowledge of legal norms and the ability to apply them is far from all that is relevant for real countermeasures against the modern challenges of a globalized society and economic transformation in our time. Problems of deontological direction play no less significant role than narrowly legal skills. Among the key new social principles to which a lawyer is obliged to adhere is the observance of the principle of equality, non-discrimination and the use of means to fight corruption.

It should also be noted that the sphere of operation of the enterprise or institution has a significant impact on the functioning of the legal service. Let's focus on the field of agro-industrial complex, as it has its own characteristics.

In our opinion, the following are deontological approaches in the functioning of the legal service in the field of agribusiness:

- Predictive, that is, legal documents should reflect not only current rules and regulations, but also contain the company's development strategy, indicate its policy and try to predict future problems and challenges. An anticipatory deontological approach should offer a contemporary focus that reflects the challenges agribusinesses face today and are likely to face tomorrow.

- Project, which characterizes the work of the legal department at all stages of decision-making. The management of the enterprise cannot make decisions without the advice of experts in the field of law, it is the legal service that provides modern tools of a managerial and administrative nature.

- Analytical approach – in cooperation with other elements of the mechanism of agribusiness enterprises, the legal support department takes into account the factors of fundamental analysis of the use of the theory of production optimization.

Another feature of legal support in the field of agribusiness is compliance with the principles of environmental law, preservation and reproduction of the natural environment. Greening technologies should be aimed at improving economic and sustainable indicators of agribusiness as a result of effective use of agrochemicals and water resources, as well as achieving the main goal - increased production. Socio-economic and technical factors affect farmers, as green technologies usually require additional costs. The task of the legal department is to demonstrate side benefit from the transition to the latest technologies by avoiding significant fines and sanctioning state levers and court costs.

Foreign experience indicates the following. In emerging economies, several new organizational forms have emerged along agricultural and food value chains. These organizational forms include, among others: a partnership business model aimed at establishing economically viable cooperation, involving also actors outside the value chains (e.g. NGOs, dissemination agents, leaders communities); business platforms, incubators and centers aimed at promoting entrepreneurial and innovative agri-food ecosystems; a new generation of cooperatives and producer organizations that promote market orientation; public-private partnership - engaging stakeholders from government, business and civil society sectors to develop and regulate private standards and/or promote and evaluate sustainable development practices; funds and agribusiness spin-offs investing in, for example, new technologies to mitigate climate change or social

impact innovation in collaboration with other stakeholders public or civil society; short supply chains or public enterprises seeking to establish long-term economic stability [3, p. 8].

The activity of legal departments with such new, difficult but necessary aspects of transformations sometimes radically changes. It is important to understand that with a rapid change in social reality, the legal system does not have sufficient means of regulating relations, that is, there are gaps or conflicts in the legislation, therefore the task of legal support is to use the analogy of the law, the analogy of the law, or even the principles of law for the fact that the agribusiness enterprise functioned within legal field.

It is also worth mentioning here the value of contract law, as it can create binding norms and establish clear legal boundaries. In this case, the contractual nature of the relationship will also belong to the tasks of the legal service department of the agricultural enterprise.

In this context, European researchers point out that changing institutions shape new organizational forms in developing economies in several ways. When formal laws or standards are absent or poorly enforced, thus creating uncertainty in the outcomes of deals and relationships between partners, partnerships will develop organizational structures that compensate for this uncertainty. [4, p. 309].

Another essential deontological standard for the functioning of the legal service in agribusiness will be the implementation of the principle of encouraging communication. Social cooperation of agribusiness leaders and leaders of civil society, as well as other representatives of value chains of agri-food products, develop, organize or change joint communication to solve the problems of the modern national agro-industrial complex. Foremost among them are the urgent and complex problems of climate change, poverty, food insecurity and malnutrition, and even conflicts related to access to natural resources. These stakeholders recognize that the state, private actors, or civil society cannot solve social and environmental problems alone, nor can they take advantage of the growth opportunities typical of developing economies without new and more collaborative forms of organization.

The Law Department in Agribusiness creates a platform for building stronger interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary debate, thus bridging the gap between agribusiness governance, international development, and government regulatory policy.

International experts convincingly prove that partnerships between small owners and agribusiness companies can contribute to the development of rural areas. These benefits accrue through two channels. At the macroeconomic level, agribusiness firms create connections between agricultural and non-agricultural sectors. Because high-value crops are grown for export rather than direct consumption, smallholders need to buy fertilizers and pesticides to meet market standards. In addition, in order to get the crop to markets, growers must establish relationships with transport and logistics firms. At the microeconomic level, agribusiness firms can help alleviate constraints that prevent smallholders from using their holdings to create viable livelihoods [5, p. 68].

In general, a conclusion should be drawn about the weightiness of the implementation into educational legal standards of educational disciplines, which would emphasize the deontological, philosophical and ethical standards of the legal specialty. We can represent our conclusion by using the research of Chinese scientists who studied the career orientations and values of more than 1000 law students in Beijing, Hong Kong and Taipei who studied in different systems of legal education in China. Their conclusions indicate that those future lawyers have a "materialistic" career orientation, those who have not studied moral and ethical disciplines related to the profession, but are more inclined to adhere to professional legal ideals, those who study in a system that emphasizes legal ethics, and are more likely to deal with issues including protection of public interest [6, p. 1129].

Conclusions

The significant role of deontological attractions in the functioning of legal services in the field of agribusiness is determined.

The following deontological approaches in the functioning of the legal service in the field of agribusiness are distinguished: prognostic (an anticipatory approach, which should offer a modern focus that

reflects the future problems of agribusiness); project (characterizes the work of the legal department at all stages of decision-making); analytical approach (including the legal support department takes into account the factors of fundamental analysis of the use of the theory of production optimization).

Emphasis is placed on the need to implement the following deontological principles in the functioning of the legal service in the field of agribusiness, among them the promotion of greening of the production sphere; implementation of the latest forms of business organization; ensuring the interests of civil society and territorial communities; complementary approach of partnership relations of all subjects of agro-industrial policy in the state.

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